

COVERAGE OF CURRENT SOCIAL ISSUES IN THE ESSAY

Iroda Nasimova

Journalism and mass media in Uzbekistan
University of Communications

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the most popular essays in the genre of essays in the world of Uzbek and world journalism. It has been pointed out that both literary and journalistic directions of the essay are cross-cutting genres.

Due to its artistic nature, journalism has been included in the literature in a broad sense since ancient times. The literature is traditionally divided into two:

- a) fiction;
- b) journalism.

By itself, the essay genre is a genre related to journalism. But do all the works created in this direction, which combine the features of analysis, research, figurative generalization, belong to journalism? The monograph "Artistic journalistic skills" says: "Any journalistic work is, of course, a journalistic work. But any journalistic work cannot be a journalistic work, it cannot rise to its level. Journalism is more quantitative, and journalism is measured and evaluated by quality. . It covers life more broadly, on a larger scale, develops the idea and grows it to great social conclusions, in this sense, the

type of journalistic creativity can be equated with politics, journalism with ideology. It is also possible to use the concepts of "speed", differentiality, relevance, relevance, integrity in relation to journalism.

Although the essay, which is an integral genre of fiction, has not appeared in Uzbek journalism for a long time, it is known that for its development there is a great source for the study of scientific, journalistic, artistic, historical, philosophical, memoir works. Elements of essays (reflection, philosophical thinking, experience) can be found in novels, short stories, short stories, and even pamphlets with a scientific approach.

For example, a person who reads only Ozod Sharafiddinov's scientific articles on literary processes is involuntarily attracted

to it as if he were reading a work of art. Researcher Marhabo Kochkarova says in her dissertation: "The most captivating aspect of reading Ozod Sharafiddinov's articles is the very sincere and emotional impact of his style." This characteristic of works of fiction can be found in many articles by Ozod Sharafiddinov. "Literature is the greatest and most glorious of all the miracles, of all the great inventions, that man has discovered. It is a wonderful spring. It is such a spring that it has the purity of tears, the ringing of a girl's bell like a bell, and the color of a rainbow."¹

It's not just a series of dry, lifeless, or silent words. It reflects the fair, honest assessment of the scholar's years of experience, as well as his poetic heart and ability to feel literature deeply. However, it is interesting that at the time of writing the first scientific and literary thoughts of the scientist, the term "essay" was not yet used in Uzbek literature. As we read the article, we realized that this article literally meets the requirements of the essay genre. Thus, Ozod Sharafiddinov's eloquent, pathetic style of writing about various literary, scientific, artistic, domestic, and religious issues, which is inherent in the nature of the essay genre, appeared from the very beginning of his scientific career. According to Umarali Normatov, the genre of essays has not suddenly appeared in the works of literary critics in recent years, or rather in the post-independence period. In fact, his appearances, essays, scientific, artistic-publicistic, critical-biographical research in the genre of fiction are reflected in his work in the 60s and 70s. However, as mentioned above, the term "essay" was not yet popular

in Uzbek literature. Let alone Uzbek literature, even in Russian literature in the 60s and 70s, there was an opinion that essays were a genre typical of Western literature, and that we did not have such works.

Today, essays in Uzbek literature and journalism are presented in two directions.

1. Artistic and journalistic essays.
2. Literary-critical essays

World literary criticism, especially in Uzbek journalism, weighs heavily on the scale of the subject, as fiction essays are relatively free. For example, Said Ahmad's "What I Lost and Found", Odil Yakubov's "Children's Duty", Ozod Sharafutdinov's "Pages of Sardaftar", Kibriyo Qahhorova's "Chorak asr hamnafas", H. Qodiri's "About my father", Otayor's "I came to see the sun", Ashura Essays by Erkin Azam "Morning Dreams", Nazar Eshankul's "From Me" to "I", Mirpolat Mirzo's "Vatan", "Surur", Askad Mukhtor, Pirimkul Kadyrov, Shukrullo, Matyokub Kushjanov, Aziz Kayumov, Laziz Qayumov, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Aripov, Utkir Hoshimov, Ibrahim Gafurov, Muhammad Ali, Dadahon Nuriy and other writers, critics and publicists can be cited as bright examples.

In world literature, especially in Russian literature, the authors of the trilogy Maria Rilke, Marina Tsvetaeva, Boris Pasternak, as well as the essays of E. Hemingway, A. Camus, Lee Ho Chul, Paulo Coelho are bright examples of the art of journalism.

In general, art journalism is one of the most important areas of journalism, which always answers the questions of the time,

¹ Kochkarova M. Artistic speech and spiritual landscapes. T. Editor n. 2015.

takes people one step ahead and leads them to a goal, reveals their pain.

For example, P. Buchanan's *The Destruction of the West* is a shining example. In recent years, new facets of political globalization have begun to appear, on the surface, unexpected "fevers." Patrick Buchanan, a Republican who ran for president in 1992 and 1996, published a 2002 book, *The Destruction of the West*. Several chapters from this book were published in the January 2007 issue of *World Literature*. It discusses the sources and factors of threats to the United States and European countries, as well as their consequences. After reading an excerpt from the work, we decided to add it, of course, to the series of journalistic essays.

From the foreword:

"Pat, we are losing our homeland ... I heard these words from many men and women in different parts of America during the 2000 election campaign. So what did they mean?"

The fact that this preface is based on a method of dialogization is also an important feature of the essay today. Buchanan's book addresses the fact that Americans, white supremacists, Europe (excluding Albania), the United States, Canada, Australia, and Japan are losing their homeland, Western civilization is on the decline, and by the middle of the 21st century, whites are the majority in the world. is devoted to proving that no state can survive.

It's not just about the composition of the population. The point is that the values, culture and way of life in these countries are becoming "Asian-African-Latin American." After the collapse of the USSR, do you have a political position, an economic opportunity, a military power or an ideological and moral influence on other

regions, the prestige of the dollar - why is the United States, the only superpower in all respects, now on the brink of collapse? How can Western civilization, which has created a "paradise on earth" for itself, be in crisis? Buchanan tries to explain the reasons for this:

"In 1960, 16 million Americans were not European in origin. Today, that number has risen to 80 million. "Every year, about a million official and another half a million illegal immigrants enter the United States."

"The influx of migrants threatens to turn a country we know, with its own traditions and culture, into a completely different country with a different history, folklore, language, culture, religion, and ancestry."

"In the near future, NATO will work to protect the area where retirees live."

"There have been 40 million abortions in the United States since it was allowed."

"The richer the state, the fewer children are born and the faster the nation disappears. If the main goal of a society is to give people as much fun, freedom and happiness as possible, then such a society has actually started to prepare funerals for these people."

"Young American girls are in no hurry to get married when they realize they can be independent and free. The number of unmarried girls between the ages of twenty and twenty-four rose from 36 percent in 1970 to 68 percent in 1993."

Buchanan's work was written in this spirit from beginning to end. Buchanan reaffirms the principle that "spirituality is the most important factor in the development of the nation" based on the bitter experience of Western countries, the need to educate generations in the spirit of national values. Buchanan's position in the

essay is noteworthy in that it is aimed at informing and warning people about the

spiritual future of the whole universe, the bitter consequences of the recessions in it.

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